

A Descriptive Study on Neutrophil to Lymphocyte Ratio as a Predictor of Myocardial Damage and Cardiac Dysfunction in Acute Coronary Syndrome Patients

Srikanth S¹, Puneet Dewan²

¹MD Medicine

²DNB Medicine

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Srikanth S

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are responsible for 32% of all deaths worldwide and are the number one cause of deaths globally not only in high-income countries but also in low- and middle-income nations. Recently, neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has been found to be a strong predictor of adverse outcomes after Acute coronary syndromes (ACS). The possible mechanism is inflammation associated with atherosclerosis and its acute manifestation. This ratio can be accessed easily and is inexpensive. However, the prognostic value of NLR over and above the traditional cardiac biomarkers is unknown.

Aims and Objectives: The aim of study was to evaluate the prognostic role of NLR in patients with ACS. To correlate NLR with existing ACS cardiac biomarkers and evaluate incremental value of NLR for predicting adverse clinical outcomes after ACS over traditional markers. To correlate NLR with ST segment score in ST elevation MI (STEMI) and with left ventricular systolic function after ACS.

Methodology: A total of 100 consecutive ACS patients were included in the study after screening for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Informed consent was taken from the patient. Besides the demographic history, cardiac risk factors, clinical presentation and diagnosis were noted for all. NLR calculated as total neutrophil count divided by total lymphocyte count was computed for all included patients. An assessment of the inflammatory markers like LDH and cardiac function parameters like CPK, CK-MB was done. All patients underwent 2D echocardiography by an experienced cardiologists and left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) was assessed for all. ST segment score was noted for patients with STEMI.

Results: NLR was positively correlated (significant statistically) with total leucocyte count (TLC) ($r = 0.28$), AST ($r = 0.37$), LDH ($r = 0.46$), CK-MB ($r = 0.35$), CPK ($r = 0.46$) and ST segment score ($r=0.56$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 . NLR co-related negatively LVEF ($r = -0.26$) ($p < 0.05$). NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters. As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically ($P=0.0058$). There was no significant correlation of the NLR ratio with the gender or comorbidity related predictors.

Interpretation and Conclusions: This study concludes that the NLR is a good predictor for myocardial damage as well as impaired cardiac contractility. The NLR can help in early prognostication of ACS severity as well and help initiate treatment therapies to prevent adverse outcomes like mortality. Its role in predicting adverse clinical outcomes can be utilized in improving the management protocols in cardiology units. The findings of our study are in accordance with the published national and international literature in this domain. We have limited Indian studies on this domain and our study adds to the limited pool of literature concerning NLR role in ACS outcome and severity prediction. Larger randomized trials with multicentric study designs need to be conducted to further validate the findings in this study. Incorporation of NLR as an early bedside investigation in risk stratification of the patients also needs to be explored further

Keywords: Acute coronary syndromes, Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio, Cardio vascular diseases, ST elevation MI.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are responsible for 32% of all deaths worldwide and are the number one cause of deaths globally not only in high-

income countries but also in low- and middle-income nations. [1] An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, of these deaths,

85% were due to heart attack and stroke. Out of the 17 million premature deaths (under the age of 70) due to non-communicable diseases in 2019, 38% were caused by CVDs. [2-7] it is important to detect cardiovascular disease as early as possible so that management with counselling and medicines can begin. Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is high-risk manifestation of coronary atherosclerosis, which includes ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), non-ST segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) and unstable angina. [8-15] the term acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is applied to patients in whom there is a suspicion or confirmation of acute myocardial ischemia or infarction. It is most commonly caused by the rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque with subsequent thrombus formation, followed by ischemia and often the necrosis of dependent heart muscle. STEMI is due to red thrombus formation often leads to acute vessel occlusion, while for NSTEMI a non-occluding (mural) platelet rich thrombus is the cause.

Aim and Objectives

To evaluate incremental value of NLR for predicting adverse clinical outcomes after ACS over traditional cardiac marker.

Methodology

All patients admitted to Command hospital (Air force) Bengaluru with the diagnosis of ACS were included in the study after informed consent. Patients diagnosed as ACS visiting emergency department were included in the study. NLR, calculated as total neutrophil counts divided by total lymphocyte counts, will be computed from the absolute values of neutrophils and lymphocytes from the same blood sample collected at admission. Since the study was a descriptive study, so a sample of convenience was taken based on historical trends of ACS patients' turnout in the cardiology department of the hospital. The data was

compiled and analyzed using MS Excel (R) office 365, GraphPad prism 8.4.2 and SPSS version 25.

Results

The study was performed at the Department of medicine in the command hospital, Bangalore on 100 consecutive patients who presented with ACS. Total number of patients included in the study were 100. It was seen that most of the patients (45%) in the study had STEMI (ST elevation MI) followed by NSTEMI seen in 38%. Unstable angina was seen in 17% patients. The average age of the patients was 55.32 ± 13.71 years with a range of 16 years to 82 years. The median age was 58 years with an interquartile range of 45 to 66.25 years. Most of the patients were over the age of 60 years (42%) followed by 40-60 years age group (40%). There was a male preponderance in the study (79%). The average BMI was 23.46 ± 2.21 kg/m² with a median BMI of 23.30 kg/m². The average NLR ratio was 6.78 ± 6.84 with a median ratio of 3.61. The interquartile range for the NLR ratio was 2.40 to 8.56. The range of NLR seen in the study was 1.69 to 31.33. A summary of the baseline hematological parameters has been given below. The average Hemoglobin level was 11.72 ± 2.29 g/dl, TLC was 12.99 ± 7.44 '000/cu mm, RBC count was 4.29 ± 1.01 '000/cu mm and the platelet count were 341.85 ± 199.65 '000/cu mm.

A correlation of the NLR with the continuous predictor variables was done. It was seen in Table 1 that –

1. NLR was positively correlated (significant statistically) with the TLC ($r=0.28$), neutrophils ($r=0.81$), AST ($r=0.37$), LDH ($r=0.46$), CK-MB ($r=0.35$), CPK ($r=0.46$) and ST segment deviation ($r=0.56$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 .
2. NLR was negatively correlated with LVEF ($r=-0.2$). The P values for these correlations were <0.05 .

Table 1: NLR correlation with the predictor variables (continuous)

Predictor	Pearson r	95% CI	R squared	P value	Significant	Correlation
Demographic parameters						
Age	0.064	-0.13 to 0.26	0.004	0.5302	No	r
BMI	-0.017	-0.21 to 0.18	0.0003	0.8635	No	r
Hematological parameters						
Hemoglobin	-0.16	-0.34 to 0.041	0.024	0.12	No	r
TLC	0.28	0.087 to 0.45	0.077	0.005	Yes	r
RBC	-0.19	-0.37 to 0.011	0.035	0.0635	No	r
Platelet count	0.08	-0.12 to 0.27	0.0064	0.4294	No	r
MCV	0.16	-0.035 to 0.35	0.026	0.1062	No	r
MCH	0.14	-0.061 to 0.33	0.019	0.173	No	r
MCHC	-0.028	-0.22 to 0.17	0.00077	0.7847	No	r
PCV	-0.13	-0.32 to 0.067	0.017	0.1931	No	r
Neutrophils	0.81	0.73 to 0.87	0.66	<0.0001	Yes	R
Lymphocytes	-0.8	-0.86 to -0.72	0.64	<0.0001	Yes	R

Monocytes	-0.33	-0.49 to -0.14	0.11	0.0008	Yes	R
Eosinophils	-0.19	-0.37 to 0.0091	0.035	0.0616	No	R
Basophils	0.043	-0.16 to 0.24	0.0018	0.674	No	R
Liver/Kidney parameters						
AST	0.37	0.18 to 0.53	0.13	0.0002	Yes	r
ALT	0.023	-0.17 to 0.22	0.00055	0.8168	No	r
Creatinine	-0.14	-0.33 to 0.060	0.019	0.1694	No	r
Inflammatory/cardiac markers						
LDH	0.46	0.29 to 0.60	0.21	<0.0001	Yes	r
CK-MB	0.35	0.16 to 0.51	0.12	0.0004	Yes	r
CPK	0.46	0.29 to 0.61	0.22	<0.0001	Yes	r
Cardiac parameters						
EF (57-75%)	-0.26	-0.44 to -0.068	0.068	0.0087	Yes	r
ST segment score parameters						
ST segment score	0.56	0.31 to 0.73	0.31	<0.0001	Yes	r

An NLR correlation with the categorical predictors was also done using the spearman rank coefficient (rho). It was seen that –

1. NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters.

As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically (P=0.0058).

2. There was no significant correlation of the NLR ratio with the gender or comorbidity related predictors.

Table 2: NLR and mortality status

NLR and mortality status	No mortality	Mortality +	P value
Number	94	6	<0.0001
Mean NLR	6.54	10.58	
Std Dev	1.93	4.80	

A receiver operator curve (ROC) was plotted to assess the ability of various markers in ACS to predict adverse outcome (mortality). The area under the curve was a measure of effectiveness of these markers. It was observed that -

1. The NLR ratio had an AUC of 0.694 which was comparable to the LDH (AUC=0.696) and CK-MB (AUC=0.743).
2. The NLR ratio was a better marker for mortality compared to the CPK (AUC=0.653).
3. The results for NLR ratio in predicting mortality was significant statistically (P=0.006) as seen in Table 1.

Discussion

NLR is a very well-established parameter for systemic inflammation. [5-17] It is a very readily available biomarker of systemic inflammation which can predict survival, independent of tumor or disease stage in various cancers and associates with cancer-related cachexia. Kamelia et. al. [17] showed that the NLR ratio can be used in the TBDM spectrum for predicting the systemic inflammation and is associated with recurrence and survival. The role of NLR in various cardiac conditions has been explored extensively by studies in recent times. Chen Chen et al [15] in their study showed that the NLR is a strong predictor of

myocardial damage in acute myocardial patients. High NLR are associated with myocardial dysfunction in all the patients. Severe inflammation (NLR) can predict the consequence of the heart in patients with coronary syndrome. Arbel et al [7] showed that Higher Neutrophil/Lymphocyte Ratio Is Related to Lower Ejection Fraction and Higher Long-term All-Cause Mortality in ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction Patients. Because of limited literature on NLR utility in Indian subset of cardiac patients, we performed at the Department of medicine in the command hospital, Bangalore on 100 consecutive patients who presented with signs and symptoms suggestive of acute coronary syndrome (ACS).

A holistic spectrum of ACS patients was used which comprised of the mostly STEMI patients (45%) and NSTEMI patients (38%). We included 17% patients in the study who had unstable angina. Overall Indian studies have also reported a predominance of the STEMI in patients presenting with ACS. Patel and Mohanan et al [18] showed that 37% of the patients were STEMI in their study followed by 31% NSTEMI patients. Chen Chen et al [15] showed that the mean age of ACS patients included in their study for the NLR evaluation, was 61.38 (±9.84) years, and 417 (58.32%) of these patients were men. This corroborated with our

study where male preponderance was seen. Mohanan et al [18] in a similar study based out of Kerala similarly showed that the mean age of participants was 60.4 (12.1) years, and more than three-quarters of these patients were men. Chen Chen et al [15] showed that The NLR ranges from 0.50 to 46 (medium \pm SD, 2.76 ± 2.96) in 715 patients. NLR positively correlated with myocardial damage (NLR vs. CK-MB: $p < 0.0001$) but negatively correlated with myocardial function (NLR vs. EF: $p < 0.0001$; NLR vs. FS: $p < 0.0001$). Myocardial damage markers (CK, CK-MB, ASL, LDH) were significantly increased, and cardiac contractile parameters (EF and FS) were reduced at $\text{NLR} > 2.76$ compared to those of $\text{NLR} < 2.76$.

Our study also showed that NLR could also be a good predictor of the ST segment score as suggested by the fact that the NLR was positively correlated with the ST Segment score ($r=0.56$). It can, therefore, be a good marker for the STEMI patients where severity of myocardial damage in STEMI can be prognosticated using this simple cost-effective test. NLR was positively correlated with mortality status with a rho level of 0.27 suggestive of a moderate positive association between the two parameters. As the outcome status changed from survival to mortality, the NLR ratio was seen to increase. The results were significant statistically ($P=0.0058$). This suggests that the NLR ratio is a good marker for the mortality prediction in the ACS patients. Arbel et al [7] showed that Patients undergoing STEMI were put into two groups (high/low NLR), and logistic regression was used to assess in-hospital complications and LVEF based on NLR. The results showed that higher NLR values (>6.5) were associated with lower EF and increased 30 days and 5-year mortality. This corresponding cut off was 3.47 for our study.

Comparative profile – NLR higher levels with lower levels

Using the cut off of NLR as 4 as per Chen Chen [15], we divided the patients into two groups. We observed that the AST levels were significantly higher for the patients with NLR more than 4 (89.22 vs 48.89, $P=0.0003$). The cardiac markers for myocardial damage like CPK (322.07 vs 141.81, $P<0.0001$) and CK-MB (90.46 vs 54.02, $P<0.0001$) and the inflammatory markers like LDH (353.78 vs 257.52, $P=0.0002$) were significantly higher for the patients with NLR more than 4.

The cardiac function parameters or cardiac contractility indicators like EF was significantly worse for patients with NLR more than 4. The results were significant statistically ($P<0.05$). The average ST segment score for the patients with NLR more than 4 was significantly higher compared to the other groups (4.48 vs 3.25, $P<0.0001$). The above findings are suggestive of

the fact that as the NLR levels increase, the cardiac function tends to worsen, and cardiac myocardial inflammatory damage increases. This trend is valid for the STEMI as well where the extent of severity, as suggested by the ST segment elevation, increased as the NLR levels increased. We observed that the mortality in the study was 06%. The average NLR levels were higher for the patients experiencing mortality suggesting a possible role of NLR in prediction of mortality and poor prognosis.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, we could conclude that the NLR is a good predictor for myocardial damage as well as impaired cardiac contractility. The NLR can help in early prognostication of STEMI severity. It's role in predicting adverse clinical outcomes can be utilized in improving the management protocols in cardiology units. The findings of our study are in accordance with the published national and international literature in this domain. We have limited Indian studies on this domain and our study adds to the limited pool of literature concerning NLR role in ACS outcome and severity prediction. Larger randomized trials with multicentric study designs need to be conducted to further validate the findings in this study. Incorporation of NLR as an early inexpensive and readily available prognostic marker in ACS can help stratify the ACS patients in resource deprived countries like India and hence needs further exploration.

References

1. Kuklina EV, Yoon PW, Keenan NL. Prevalence of coronary heart disease risk factors and screening for high cholesterol levels among young adults, United States, 1999–2006. *The Annals of Family Medicine*. 2010 Jul 1; 8(4):327-33.
2. Thygesen K, Alpert JS, Jaffe AS, Chaitman BR, Bax JJ, Morrow DA, White HD, Executive Group on behalf of the Joint European Society of Cardiology (ESC)/American College of Cardiology (ACC)/American Heart Association (AHA)/World Heart Federation (WHF) Task Force for the Universal Definition of Myocardial Infarction. Fourth universal definition of myocardial infarction (2018). *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*. 2018 Oct 30; 72(18):2231-64.
3. Tehrani DM, Gardin JM, Yanez D, Hirsch CH, Lloyd-Jones DM, Stein PK, Wong ND. Impact of inflammatory biomarkers on relation of high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol with incident coronary heart disease: cardiovascular Health Study. *Atherosclerosis*. 2013 Dec 1; 231(2):246-51.

4. Osadnik T, Strzelczyk J, Hawranek M, Lekston A, Wasilewski J, Kurek A, Gutowski AR, Wilczek K, Dyrbuś K, Gierlotka M, Wiczkowski A. Red cell distribution width is associated with long-term prognosis in patients with stable coronary artery disease. *BMC cardiovascular disorders*. 2013 Dec; 13(1):1-8.
5. Han YC, Yang TH, Kim DI, Jin HY, Chung SR, Seo JS, Jang JS, Kim DK, Kim DK, Kim KH, Seol SH. Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio predicts long-term clinical outcomes in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention. *Korean Circulation Journal*. 2013 Feb 1; 43(2):93-9.
6. Azab B, Zaher M, Weiserbs KF, Torbey E, Lacossiere K, Gaddam S, Gobunsuy R, Jadonath S, Baldari D, McCord D, Lafferty J. Usefulness of neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio in predicting short-and long-term mortality after non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction. *The American journal of cardiology*. 2010 Aug 15; 106(4):470-6.
7. Arbel Y, Finkelstein A, Halkin A, Birati EY, Revivo M, Zuzut M, Shevach A, Berliner S, Herz I, Keren G, Banai S. Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio is related to the severity of coronary artery disease and clinical outcome in patients undergoing angiography. *Atherosclerosis*. 2012 Dec 1; 225(2):456-60.
8. Maxwell SR, Lip GY. Reperfusion injury: a review of the pathophysiology, clinical manifestations, and therapeutic options. *International journal of cardiology*. 1997 Jan 31; 58(2):95-117.
9. Lindahl B, Toss H, Siegbahn A, Venge P, Wallentin L. Markers of myocardial damage and inflammation in relation to long-term mortality in unstable coronary artery disease. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2000 Oct 19; 343(16):1139-47.
10. Sugiyama S, Okada Y, Sukhova GK, Virmani R, Heinecke JW, Libby P. Macrophage myeloperoxidase regulation by granulocyte macrophage colony-stimulating factor in human atherosclerosis and implications in acute coronary syndromes. *The American journal of pathology*. 2001 Mar 1; 158(3):879-91.
11. Shao B, Oda MN, Oram JF, Heinecke JW. Myeloperoxidase: an inflammatory enzyme for generating dysfunctional high density lipoprotein. *Current opinion in cardiology*. 2006 Jul 1; 21(4):322-8.
12. Krishnaswamy G, Kelley J, Yerra L, Smith JK, Chi DS. Human endothelium as a source of multifunctional cytokines: molecular regulation and possible role in human disease. *Journal of interferon & cytokine research*. 1999 Feb 1; 19(2):91-104.
13. Kumar AG, Ballantyne CM, Michael LH, Kukielka GL, Youker KA, Lindsey ML, Hawkins HK, Birdsall HH, MacKay CR, LaRosa GJ, Rossen RD. Induction of monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 in the small veins of the ischemic and reperfused canine myocardium. *Circulation*. 1997 Feb 4; 95(3):693-700.
14. Motwani JG, Struthers AD, McAlpine H, Kennedy N. Plasma brain natriuretic peptide as an indicator for angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibition after myocardial infarction. *The Lancet*. 1993 May 1; 341(8853):1109-13.
15. Chen C, Cong BL, Wang M, Abdullah M, Wang XL, Zhang YH, Xu SJ, Cui L. Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio as a predictor of myocardial damage and cardiac dysfunction in acute coronary syndrome patients. *Integrative medicine research*. 2018 Jun 1; 7(2):192-9.
16. Barker T, Fulde G, Moulton B, Nadauld LD, Rhodes T. An elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio associates with weight loss and cachexia in cancer. *Scientific reports*. 2020 May 5; 10(1):1-6.
17. Kamelia T, Guno TH, Subardi S, Mansjoer A, Harbuwono DS. Neutrophil-lymphocyte count ratio (nlr) was associated with disease activity in tuberculosis and diabetic mellitus patients. *In respirology* 2018 Nov 1; 23:204.
18. Mohanan PP. Channelling regional registries for optimization of cardiac care: lessons from around the world. *European heart journal*. 2013; 34:83-5.